

PROTECTED AREAS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract:

This article examines the organization of protected areas in the Republic of Uzbekistan, their use, the analysis of data such as flora and fauna in these areas. New recommendations for preserving nature, animal and plant life have been proposed.

Keywords:

State nature reserves, State national nature parks, State nature monuments, Red book, Plants, Animal world, Nature, Forest.

Introduction:

The preservation and protection of the natural environment in Uzbekistan has been increasing rapidly since the independence of Uzbekistan. First of all, this is explained by the correct conduct of the state policy of Uzbekistan, and secondly, it is due to the fact that the Uzbek people living in our country have been honoring mother nature since ancient times. This situation is clearly reflected even in the customs and traditions of our people. Especially, after gaining independence, Uzbekistan raised nature conservation and protection to the level of state policy. Large-scale reforms are being carried out in this regard. A lot of laws and decisions, legal normative documents have been adopted on nature protection. For example, a collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on improving the system of payments for environmental pollution and disposal of waste in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on protected natural areas collection, legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the establishment of the republican research and production center for ornamental horticulture and forestry under the General Directorate of Forestry of the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources collection, collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the norms of use of bioresources, collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the implementation of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on protected natural areas, special use of nature The collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the improvement of the system of payments, the collection of legal documents of the Republic of

Uzbekistan on the program of environmental protection works of the Republic of Uzbekistan, among them. According to Article 5 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protected Natural Areas", protected natural areas are divided into the following categories according to their purpose and regime:

- state reserves;
- complex (landscape) order reserves;
- state national nature parks;
- historical monuments;
- areas intended for preservation, reproduction and restoration of certain natural objects and complexes;
- protected landscapes;
- areas designated for the management of certain natural resources.

The establishment of nature reserves in our country and the establishment and expansion of specially protected areas based on them have an incomparable place in the protection of the nature of the territory of our Republic. In addition to nature reserves, the creation of national parks, reserves and similar areas is mainly based on nature reserves.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has joined several international conventions in the field of nature protection, including the Convention on Biodiversity Conservation. Our country attaches great importance to these international documents. Currently, the system of protected areas includes 9 state reserves with a total area of 2,164 km², 2 national parks with an area of 6,061 km², 9 state reserves with an area of 12,186.5 km², and 1 republic rare animal breeding center. But only 1.8% of protected areas are long-term. This is definitely not enough. Reserves make up 10% of the system of protected areas of the country. With the creation of the Ugam Chotkal National Park in 1976, National Parks make up 30% of the total protected area. State order offices make up 39% of protected areas.

The system of protected areas is extremely unevenly distributed across regions and natural ecological zones of Uzbekistan. Most of them belong to Tashkent region. It should be noted that protected natural areas have not become an element of the overall regional development strategy.

Setting the problem. The system of protected areas is extremely unevenly distributed across regions and natural ecological zones of Uzbekistan.

Nowadays, the environmental condition of nature is disturbed, the soil, air and water are polluted with harmful substances, the useful species of plants and animals are decreasing, that is, they are used as food, grasslands, orchards and

mountains feeding animals on the slopes, cutting down bushes and trees, and burning the dry leaves of trees in the fall and poisoning the environment with the harmful gases emitted from them are among the current problems.

40-45 years ago, the rivers and streams of the plain were covered with dense forests and reed beds, and trees and bushes such as turangil, willow, and cypress grew thickly in the forests. But unfortunately, in recent years, due to the construction of dams, reservoirs and canals, the decrease of river and stream water, the level of seepage water has decreased, and as a result of their mineralization and salinity, the number of these forests is increasing, especially in the lower Amudarya.

Development of new lands, construction of new cities and roads in the desert zone, construction of new mines, and as mentioned above, the harmful and poisonous gases released from them first of all spread into the atmosphere and seriously affect people, flora and fauna. it's a secret.

Research analysis and results. The system of protected areas is unevenly distributed across regions and natural ecological zones of Uzbekistan.

The forest area in the valleys of the Republic is 210,000 hectares. Trees such as juniper, orange, acacia, willow, poplar, maple, pine and maple grow in it. Currently, in order to increase the forest area from 210 thousand hectares, the following measures should be taken:

- Preventing the death of young shoots;
- Recovery of forest resources and increase control;
- Protecting forests from fire, various pests and diseases, contamination with toxic and chemical substances.

In addition, the following studies should be conducted to improve the condition of pastures and restore them:

- Proper use of pastures;
- Purposeful use of large areas in Togoldi and semi-desert zones in agriculture;
- growing saxophone trees in the desert and not cutting them;
- Breeding of valuable trees and shrubs in the mountains, such as juniper;
- Adherence to the standard of keeping sheep and cattle in pastures.

It is worth noting that protected areas should be established in each region, all protected plants and animals should be brought there, and measures should be taken to preserve them. It is true that such regions are currently organized, but, as mentioned above, they are not evenly distributed across regions.

It is necessary to organize such areas, plant all kinds of trees there, and create all the necessary conditions for animals and plants. Because each plant that each

bird eats is different. Every place will be supplied with water, i.e. nests will be built for birds, drip irrigation technologies will be installed. They also create conditions for animals to live in accordance with themselves.

Summary. Protected natural areas were not part of the overall regional development strategy.

By ecologically evaluating such protected areas, if we evaluate the results of the analysis based on the above methods, the environmental condition of nature will be disturbed, the soil, air and water will be polluted with substances harmful to life, and the risk of the reduction of useful species of plants and animals is high. decreases. Nature protection works will be started as a result of clearing the bushes and trees on the meadows, groves and mountain slopes. As a result of this activity, the possibility of further conservation of our nature increases.

It can also be noted that the development and expansion of nature reserves in our country is the main activity that must be carried out in nature protection. Because of this, it is the duty of each of us to protect such areas, to preserve all the gifts of nature, to pass them on to the next generation.

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